

INTEGRO-DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada integro-differensial tenglamalar sistemasi uchun Koshi masalasi yechimi Dalamber usulidan foydalanib aniqlangan.*

Quyidagi

$$(1) \quad \begin{cases} x'(t) = aI_{m^+}^\gamma x(t) + bI_{m^+}^\gamma y(t) + f_1(t), \\ y'(t) = cI_{m^+}^\gamma x(t) + dI_{m^+}^\gamma y(t) + f_2(t), \end{cases} \quad t > m$$

sistemasining

$$(2) \quad x(m) = x_0, y(m) = y_0$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini topish masalasini qaraylik, bu yerda $I_{m^+}^\gamma$ kasr tartibli Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi integral operator bo'lib [1], u quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$I_{m^+}^\gamma z(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_m^t (t-s)^{\gamma-1} z(s) ds,$$

$\Gamma(z)$ - Eylerning gamma funksiyasi [2], $\gamma, a, b, c, d, x_0, y_0$ - berilgan haqiqiy sonlar bo'lib, $\gamma > 0$; $f_1(t)$ va $f_2(t)$ berilgan funksiyalar, $x(t)$ va $y(t)$ lar esa noma'lum funksiyalar.

{(1),(2)} masala yechimini Dalamber usulidan foydalanib topamiz. [3],[4] ishlarda ham Dalamber usulidan foydalanib, ba'zi tenglamalar sistemasi uchun Koshi masalasining yechimi formulalari oshkor ko'rinishda topilgan.

{(1),(2)} Koshi masalasining yechimini topish bilan shug'ullanamiz. Shu maqsadda (1) ning ikkinchi tenglamasini λ songa ko'paytirib birinchi tenglamaga qo'shamiz. Natijada quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$(3) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \{x(t) + \lambda y(t)\} = (a + \lambda c) I_{m^+}^\gamma x(t) + (b + \lambda d) I_{m^+}^\gamma y(t) + f_1(t) + \lambda f_2(t).$$

Oxirgi tenglikni quyidagi ko'rinishda qayta yozib olamiz:

$$(4) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \{x(t) + \lambda y(t)\} = (a + \lambda c) I_{m^+}^\gamma \left[x(t) + \frac{b + \lambda d}{a + \lambda c} y(t) \right] + f_1(t) + \lambda f_2(t).$$

λ sonni shunday tanlaylikki, $\frac{b + \lambda d}{a + \lambda c} = \lambda$ tenglamani qanoatlantirsin. Faraz qilaylik,

λ_1 va λ_2 lar oxirgi tenglamaning ildizlari bo'lib, $\lambda_1 \neq \lambda_2$ bo'lsin. U holda bu sonlarni (4) ga qo'yib, ushbu tenglikni hosil qilamiz:

$$(5) \quad \frac{d}{dt}\{x(t) + \lambda_i y(t)\} = (a + \lambda_i c) I_{m^+}^\gamma [x(t) + \lambda_i y(t)] + f_1(t) + \lambda_i f_2(t) \quad i=1,2.$$

Soddalik maqsadida quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritaylik:

$$(6) \quad x(t) + \lambda_i y(t) = z(t), \quad a + \lambda_i c = \tilde{\lambda}_i, \quad f_1(t) + \lambda_i f_2(t) = f_{3,i}(t), \quad i=1,2.$$

U holda (5) quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi:

$$(7) \quad \frac{d}{dt} z(t) = \tilde{\lambda}_i I_{m^+}^\gamma z(t) + f_{3,i}(t) \quad i=1,2.$$

(7) tenglamada t ni s ga almashtirib, so'ngra hosil bo'lgan tenglikni s bo'yicha $[m, t]$ oraliqda integrallaymiz. Natijada

$$(8) \quad z(t) - \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t \frac{(t-s)^\gamma}{\Gamma(\gamma+1)} f_{4,i}(s) ds = f_{4,i}(t), \quad i=1,2.$$

ko'rinishdagi 2-tur Volterra integral tenglamasiga ega bo'lamiz, bu yerda

$$f_{4,i}(t) = \int_m^t f_{3,i}(t) dt + z(m).$$

Oxirgi tenglama yechimini ketma-ket yaqinlashish usulidan foydalanib topamiz. Nolinchi yaqinlashish sifatida

$$z_0(t) = f_{4,i}(t)$$

ni qabul qilamiz. Birinchi va ikkinchi yaqinlashishlarni mos holda quyidagi formulalar bo'yicha aniqlaymiz:

$$z_1(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,s) f_{4,i}(s) ds,$$

$$z_2(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,\tau) z_1(\tau) d\tau =$$

$$= f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,\tau) \left[f_{4,i}(\tau) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^\tau K(\tau,s) f_{4,i}(s) ds \right] d\tau =$$

$$= f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,s) f_{4,i}(s) ds + \tilde{\lambda}_i^2 \int_m^t K_2(t,s) f_{4,i}(s) ds.$$

n -yaqinlashishni esa

$$z_n(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t \left[\sum_{j=0}^n \tilde{\lambda}_i^{j-1} K_j(t,s) \right] f_{4,i}(s) ds$$

formuladan foydalanib topamiz. Bu yerda $K_j(t,s)$ -iteratsiyalangan yadrolar bo'lib,

$$K_1(t,s) = K(t,s) = (t-s)^\gamma \Gamma^{-1}(\gamma+1),$$

$$K_j(t,s) = \int_s^t K(t,\tau) K_{j-1}(\tau,s) d\tau, \quad j=2,3,\dots$$

Dastlab, $K_2(t, s)$ ni hisoblaylik:

$$K_2(t, s) = \int_s^t K(t, \tau) K(\tau, s) d\tau = \int_s^t \frac{(t-\tau)^\gamma (\tau-s)^\gamma}{\Gamma^2(\gamma+1)} d\tau.$$

Ushbu almashtirishni bajaraylik: $\tau = (t-s)\eta + s$. U holda beta va gamma funksiya xossalaridan foydalansak,

$$\begin{aligned} K_2(t, s) &= \int_0^1 \frac{(t-s)^{2\gamma+1} \eta^{\gamma+1-1} (1-\eta)^{\gamma+1-1}}{\Gamma^2(\gamma+1)} d\eta = \frac{(t-s)^{2\gamma+1}}{\Gamma^2(\gamma+1)} \int_0^1 \eta^{\gamma+1-1} (1-\eta)^{\gamma+1-1} d\eta = \\ &= \frac{(t-s)^{2\gamma+1}}{\Gamma^2(\gamma+1)} B(\gamma+1, \gamma+1) = \frac{(t-s)^{2(\gamma+1)-1}}{\Gamma(2(\gamma+1))}. \end{aligned}$$

Matematik induksiya usulidan foydalanib ko'rsatish qiyin emaski, $K_j(t, s)$ uchun quyidagi o'rinli:

$$K_j(t, s) = (t-s)^{j(\gamma+1)-1} \Gamma^{-1}[j(\gamma+1)], \quad j=1, 2, 3, \dots$$

$K_j(t, s)$ dan foydalanib, $R(t, s; \tilde{\lambda}_i)$ rezolventani tuzamiz:

$$R(t, s; \tilde{\lambda}_i) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \tilde{\lambda}_i^{j-1} K_j(t, s) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_i^{j-1} (t-s)^{j(\gamma+1)-1}}{\Gamma[j(\gamma+1)]}.$$

Mittag-Leffler funksiyasining yoyilmasidan foydalansak[5], rezolventani quyidagicha yozishimiz mumkin:

$$R(t, s; \tilde{\lambda}_i) = (t-s)^{\gamma-1} E_{\gamma+1, \gamma+1} \left[\tilde{\lambda}_i (t-s)^{\gamma+1} \right].$$

U holda 2-tur Volterra integral tenglamalari nazariyasiga [6] asosan (8) tenglamani yechimi ushbu formula orqali ifodalanadi:

$$(9) \quad z(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t (t-s)^{\gamma-1} E_{\gamma+1, \gamma+1} \left[\tilde{\lambda}_i (t-s)^{\gamma+1} \right] f_{4,i}(s) ds.$$

Endi (6) va (9) tengliklarga asosan quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini tuzamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) + \lambda_i y(t) &= \\ &= f_{4,i}(t) + (a + \lambda_i c) \int_m^t (t-s)^{\gamma-1} E_{\gamma+1, \gamma+1} \left[(a + \lambda_i c)(t-s)^{\gamma+1} \right] f_{4,i}(s) ds, \quad i=1, 2. \end{aligned}$$

Oxirgi tenglamalar sistemasini algebraik qo'shish usulidan foydalanib, $x(t)$ va $x(t)$ noma'lum funksiyalarni quyidagicha bir qiymatli aniqlaymiz:

$$x(t) = f_{4,1}(t) + (a + \lambda_1 c) \int_m^t (t-s)^{\gamma-1} E_{\gamma+1, \gamma+1} \left[(a + \lambda_1 c)(t-s)^{\gamma+1} \right] f_{4,1}(s) ds - \lambda_1 y(t);$$

$$y(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \left\{ f_{4,1}(t) - f_{4,2}(t) + (a + \lambda_1 c) \int_m^t (t-s)^{\gamma-1} E_{\gamma+1, \gamma+1} \left[(a + \lambda_1 c)(t-s)^{\gamma+1} \right] f_{4,1}(s) ds - \right.$$

$$-(a + \lambda_2 c) \int_m^t (t-s)^{\gamma-1} E_{\gamma+1, \gamma+1} \left[(a + \lambda_2 c)(t-s)^{\gamma+1} \right] f_{4,2}(s) ds \Big\}.$$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. A.A.Kilbas, H.M.Srivastava and Trujilo. Theory and Applications of Fractional Differential equations. North Holland Mathematics Studies, 204p.
2. A.Q. O'rinov. Maxsus funksiyalar va maxsus operatorlar. Farg'ona: "Farg'ona" nashriyoti, 2012, -112 bet.
3. A.O.Mamanazarov, O.A.Abdubannopova. Kasr tartibli differensial operatorni o'z ichiga oluvchi chiziqli differensial tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning bir usuli haqida. O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali. 14-son. 464-467-betlar. 2022.
4. O.A.Abdubannopova. Differensial tenglamalar sistemasi uchun Koshi masalasi. O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali. 15-son. 757-761-betlar. 2023.
5. Podlubniy I. Fractional Differential Equations: An introduction to Fractional Derivatives, Fractional Differential Equations, to Methods of Their solution, Mathematics in Science and Engineering. Vol.198 Diego: Academic Press, 1999.
6. M.S. Salohiddinov. Integral tenglamalar. Toshkent: Yangiyul polygraph Service, 2007, -256 bet.